

A Study of GFRP on Stress Corrosion Cracking (Prediction of Crack Propagation Mechanisms Considering the Interfacial Degradation)

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SUMMARY: The prediction of the fracture morphology of the stress corrosion cracking (S.C.C) of GFRP laminates is reported. In the last decade, the authors investigated the relationship between the crack propagation rate da/dt and the applied stress intensity factor K in some environmental solutions, and the threshold stress intensity factor was verified. However, the crack propagation and arrest mechanism were not clarified. Recently we have investigated the degradation mechanism by single fiber fragmentation tests using E-glass and NCR-glass fibers embedded in the vinyl ester resins. The effects of the acid solution diffusion or the distilled water into the vinyl ester resin on the fiber strength and the interfacial shear strength have been evaluated as a function of the immersion time or the water absorption. As a result, although the E-glass fiber degrades due to the acid solutions, the degradation behavior of the E-glass fiber strength embedded in the resin did not change in respect to the solutions, the acid solution and the distilled water. And the interfacial shear strength also degrades as a function of the immersion time and the water absorption. It was suggested that only water diffusion affects the degradation of the inner E-glass fiber in the early time of the immersion time, and the acid would not reach the fiber because the value of the water diffusion coefficient is much larger than the acid diffusion coefficient. Furthermore, a Fickian diffusion analysis shows that the water concentration around the fiber embedded in the matrix resin already reached a saturation limit at the beginning of the acid diffusion. Therefore, it is concluded that the water diffusion affects the degradation of the fiber and the interfacial strength immediately before acid corrodes the fiber and interface. Similarly, the NCR-glass fiber strength and the NCR-glass fiber/Vinyl ester resin interface degrade due to the water diffusion. As the interfacial shear strength is degraded independently the inner fiber, it is predicted that the degradation behavior depends on both the matrix resin degradation and the reaction of the water and the silane coupling agent. In addition, the interfacial debonding energy was estimated using the stress state in the fiber and fiber/matrix interface of the fragmentation data. Based on the energy criterion, the ratio of fiber fracture energy and interfacial fracture energy is calculated in order to estimate the transition of the relationship between the penetration and the deflection. The ratio as a function of the immersion time allows the prediction of the transition, therefore the fracture morphology caused by the degradation of the interface strength is discussed in this paper.

KEYWORDS: glass fiber reinforced plastics, stress corrosion cracking, interfacial debonding, water diffusion, fiber bridging

INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) have been used for a variety of chemical applications, since they have an outstanding performance as structural materials. However, the glass fiber suffers from chemical attacks in corrosive environments although it is embedded in composite materials, and such degradation is accelerated by applied stress. The stress-corrosion cracking (S.C.C.) mechanisms should be solved in the GFRP from the point of reliability. Crack-propagation properties of woven GFRP laminates have been investigated in the last decade¹⁻⁵. The crack propagation behavior on the stress intensity factor, K_I , and the crack propagation rate, da/dt , diagram was separated into two stages and then the threshold stress intensity factor, K_{ISCC} , was confirmed on crack propagation behaviors in each environmental solution. The K_I - da/dt diagram of the C-glass/Vinyl ester (C/VE) systems under

various environmental solutions is shown in Fig.1. The acid corrosion resistance was increased compared with the E-glass/Vinyl ester systems. Microscopic observation of the crack plane showed that the failure of C-glass fibers in the matrix was independent on the acid diffusion. However, the fracture morphology was almost brittle on the C-glass fiber fracture surface independently of acid diffusion, therefore, the acid corrosion effect of C-glass fibers was not confirmed specifically in C/VE systems. Moreover fiber bridging was estimated because there were pull-out fibers on the fracture plane. Although the acid corrosion resistance of GFRP is improved using C-glass fibers as reinforcements, the results of the observation of fracture surfaces were insufficient in estimating accurate S.C.C. mechanisms. In order to estimate the corrosion and fracture mechanisms of a fiber and a fiber/matrix interface, the strength degradation was evaluated by a fragmentation test using a single fiber model composite. The results showed that the interfacial shear strength decreases as a function of the water absorption rate of the matrix. It was suggested that the interfacial degradation was caused by an increase of the water concentration around the fiber/matrix interface. The weakened interface leads to a crack deflection, which in turn leads to a transition of the crack propagation behavior due to the existence of surviving fibers, thus, the result of a single fiber composite test is a critical issue on S.C.C mechanisms in the acid corrosion resistance GFRP that is reinforced by the acid corrosion resistance of fiber. In this study, furthermore, the interfacial degradation caused by water diffusion is investigated using a DCDC test specimen with embedded fibers, and the interaction of a crack with fibers is focused upon to emphasize the effect of interfacial degradation on the crack propagation behavior.

EXPERIMENT

DCDC tests

In the woven GFRP laminates, the fiber directions are vertical and parallel to the crack propagation. The role of the fibers is to arrest the crack propagation. The crack arrest mechanisms are concerned with vertical direction primarily, therefore the arrest mechanisms are evaluated in this study. However, the crack propagation behavior in the woven laminates is complicated to observe directly and microscopically. To facilitate the direct observation, the fiber direction is suitable as unidirectional, and fibers are embedded in the matrix as a single fiber bundle to simplify the crack arrest behavior. In this specimen, the fiber volume fraction is very small, thus it is difficult to control the matrix crack propagation. The double cleavage drilled compression (DCDC) specimen is useful geometry to use for fibers that are bridging long cracks, loaded in compression a crack initiates from the center drilled hole and that runs parallel to the applied stress along the specimens mid plane^{6,7}. The geometry of the specimen is the rectangular beam (6.0×6.0×60 mm) shown in Fig.2, and to ensure that the crack runs along the mid-plane, a pre-crack with a length of 1mm were introduced. The fibers used in this study

Fig. 3 History plots of water absorption rate

were NCR-glass fibers with a diameter of $24.5\mu\text{m}$. The NCR-glass fibers have a similar superior acid resistance to the C-glass fibers. Furthermore, the weight loss due to water corrosion is less than the C-glass fibers. To focus on the interfacial degradation, it is assumed that the corrosion by water diffusion is negligible. The NCR-glass fibers were embedded in the matrix ahead of the pre-crack and the number of fibers is about 130. The matrix used was a vinyl ester resin and the vinyl ester excelled on water swelling. The mechanical properties of the fiber and matrix are shown in Table1.

Experimental procedure

To focus on the effects of the crack arrest mechanisms, the interfacial degradation was promoted by immersing specimens in distilled water at 323K. The history plots of the water absorption rate as a function of immersion time is shown in Fig.3. The specimen used was immersed for 200 hours when the specimen was saturated by water and to emphasize the effect of the interfacial degradation, intact specimens were also tested. The intact specimens correspond to the immersion time is of 0 hours. Specimens were loaded in compression with a screw-driven mechanical testing machine at a crosshead speed displacement rate of $0.1\text{mm}/\text{min}$. The crack tip was observed using an optical microscope, and interactions of a crack with a single fiber bundle are estimated by measurements of the relationship between the fiber location and the interfacial debonding length.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Matrix crack propagating behavior

Fig.4 shows the typical load-displacement diagrams. At the maximum load, the matrix crack initiated from the pre-crack tip and the propagating behavior was unstable. The fiber bundle suspended the crack propagation. The specimens were unloaded, and the photographs of the crack tip were obtained by an optical microscope. Fiber bridging was confirmed in the photographs of the crack tip (Fig.5), and the fiber/matrix interface was debonded. The interface along the fibers that existed at the location near the crack tip was not debonded. The debonding behavior was obtained on both immersed and intact specimens. Some fibers failed at the debonding zone, and no failures on the crack plane were observed. The relationships between the location of a crack tip and a fiber bundle appeared similarly on both immersed and intact specimens. Also, a fiber bridging behavior was observed in both immersed and intact specimens as shown in Fig.5. The interfacial debonding length L_d , measured by an optical microscope, is plotted as a function of the distance from the crack tip as shown in Fig.6. The interfacial debonding length L_d of the immersed specimens increases

Fig.4 Typical applied load-displacement diagrams.

Fig.5 Photograph of crack tip that is bridged by fibers.

compared with the intact specimens due to the interfacial degradation caused by water diffusion. The weak interface leads to a crack deflection, debonding along the fiber/matrix interface, and a fiber bridging between the crack planes. Crack deflection behaviors were not observed due to unstable propagation. However, it is considered that the deflection occurred on both specimens because the fibers failed at the interfacial debonding zone.

Fiber bridging stress distribution

Fiber bridging behaves as the crack arrest, such that the number of fiber bridging decreases the stress intensity factor at the crack tip. The magnitude of the crack arrest is determined by stress distribution of the fiber bridging. Because the interfacial debonding occurs by applying σ_t at the crack plane, σ_t is determined by direct measurements of L_d . Based on Sun and Singh's model, the relationship is⁸

$$\sigma_t = \frac{2 E_c \tau_f L_d}{r_f V_m E_m} + \frac{2 E_c \tau_f}{E_m V_m \rho} + \sqrt{\frac{4 E_f E_c \Gamma_i}{r_f E_m V_m}} \quad (1)$$

where Γ_i is the interfacial debonding energy, τ_f is the interfacial sliding stress and

Fig.6 Debond length profiles for the distance from the crack tip for immersion time $t_i=0$ and 200 hours.

$$\rho^2 = \frac{4 E_c G_m}{V_m E_m E_f \phi} \quad (2)$$

and

$$\phi = -\frac{2 \ln V_f + V_m (3 - V_f)}{2 V_m^2} \quad (3)$$

The interfacial debonding energy Γ_i is a material constant, and the value of the interfacial debonding energy should be measured on both immersed and intact specimens. We have investigated the interfacial debonding energy Γ_i by a fragmentation test using a single fiber composite¹⁰ and the effect on the water diffusion has been evaluated using immersed specimens. As a result, the interfacial debonding energy decreases as a function of immersion time. The value of the interfacial debonding energy was 0.45 kJ/m² as intact specimens, and the value was employed in this study. For immersed specimens, 0.20 kJ/m² was obtained and was assigned to immersed specimens. Although the immersion time on fragmentation test is different from this study, it is considered that the exposed interface has promoted degradation. Therefore, the degradation in this study corresponds to the results of a fragmentation test. Based on the interfacial debonding energies, the calculated bridging stress

distributions are shown in Fig.7. The distribution of the bridging stress of intact specimens exceeded one of immersed, because the elastic strain energy to derive crack propagation of immersed specimens is decreased by a degradation of the matrix cracking stress due to the water absorption. Moreover the debonding length and the fiber bridging stress decides the failure probability function of fibers. In the debonding region ($0 < z < L_d$), the fiber stress distribution $\sigma_f(z)$ is¹²,

$$\sigma_f(z) = \sigma_t - 2\tau_f z / r_f \quad (4)$$

where r_f is a fiber radius. By adopting the weakest link statistics and following the analysis of Oh and Finnie^{10, 11}, it is possible to derive a probability density function. Furthermore, by integrating the probability density function, the failure probability function is

$$q = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{r_f}{L_0 \sigma_0^m \tau_f (m+1)} \left\{ \left(\sigma_t - \frac{2\tau_f L_d}{r_f} \right)^{m+1} - \sigma_t^{m+1} \right\} \right] \quad (5)$$

where m and σ_0 are the Weibull parameters. The value of m is 20 and σ_0 is 2700MPa, while both values are obtained by a fragmentation test. The weight loss of an NCR-glass fiber by water diffusion

Fig.7 Comparison of bridging stress distribution for immersion time $t_i=0$ and 200 hours.

Fig.8 Comparison of the Failure probability function for immersion time $t_i=0$ and 200 hours.

is almost zero, therefore the same values were used as Weibull parameters on both immersed and intact specimens. The calculated probability function is shown in Fig.8. The distribution of the intact specimen exhibits that almost all fibers failed by the crack arrest. The failure probability function implies that the crack bridging behavior varies due to the interfacial degradation.

Toughening effect

The effects on fibers bridging and the interfacial degradation were confirmed by the DCDC test with fiber bundles and measurements of the interaction of a crack with bridging fibers. On the other hand, the contribution on a crack arrest is considered on only a single fiber bundle. In the woven GFRP laminates, a crack propagates the fiber bundle and matrix alternately. The survived fibers against crack propagation contribute to a crack arrest due to an increase of a toughening effect. The determination of toughness requires consideration of the fraction of fibers that fail at each location behind the crack tip. The traction T on the crack plane is described as¹³

$$T = V_f \{ (1-q)\sigma_t + q\sigma_p \} \quad (6)$$

where σ_p is the stress on the crack plane for failed fibers, and it is the average value of the pull-out stress based on the average failure strength. The value of $q\sigma_p$ is much smaller than $(1-q)\sigma_t$. To simplify

the issue on a interfacial degradation, the distribution of $(1-q)\sigma_t$ is focused without $q\sigma_p$. The value of $V_f(1-q)\sigma_t$ is the mean bridging stress considering the fraction of failure fibers at each location. The calculated distributions of $V_f(1-q)\sigma_t$ are shown in Fig.9. The bridging stress σ_t increased as a function of distance from a crack tip. However the mean bridging stress distribution has a peak stress value based on an increase of the failure probability function. In the DCDC tests, some bridging fibers failed on the suspension of the matrix crack propagation. The failure probability function shows the ratio of failure fibers in each direction from a crack tip. The survived fibers on the crack plane affects the arrest on resuming the matrix crack propagation, and the value of $(1-q)\sigma_t$ decides the magnitude of a crack arrest effect. The peak stress of immersed specimens appears at 1200 μm . In contrast, there are no survived fibers in intact specimens, therefore the toughening effect is hardly obtained on resumption. The differences on the mean bridging distribution between immersed and intact specimens show that the effect of water diffusion does not appear easily, because a crack deflection and bridging were occurred in the DCDC tests any way on the interfacial debonding energy. Generally, the crack propagation properties are discussed based on crack deflection and penetration. Nevertheless, it is suggested that the toughening effect on resumption of the crack propagation is complex and distinguished from the point of interfacial degradation.

Fig.9 Comparison of mean fiber bridging stress distribution immersion time $t_i=0$ and 200 hours.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The fiber bridging behavior and bridging stress distribution were confirmed by a DCDC test with a single fiber bundle. The behavior occurred independently of the interfacial shear strength.
2. The bridging stress was calculated by direct measurement of the interfacial debonding length, and it was suggested that the distribution of intact specimens exceeded immersed specimens.
3. The failure probability function shows that almost all fibers whose interface was debonded, failed at the debonding zone in the intact specimens. However, a number of fibers survived in the immersed specimens, therefore the effect on the crack arrest is superior to intact specimens. The results show that the dependence on the interfacial degradation of the crack propagation in NCR-glass/Vinyl ester systems is estimated considering the fiber bridging stress distribution.

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REFERENCES

- (1) J. N. Price and D. Hull, "Effect of Matrix Toughness on Crack Propagation during Stress Corrosion of Glass Reinforced Composites", *Composites Science and Technology*, 28, 211(1987)
- (2) Klaus Friedrich, "Stress corrosion crack propagation in glass fibre reinforced/thermoplastic PET", *Journal of Material Science*, 16, 3292(1981)
- (3) P. J. Hogg, "A Model for Stress Corrosion Crack Growth in Glass Reinforced Plastics", *Composites Science and Technology*, 38, 23(1990)
- (4) P. J. Hogg, S. N. Sapalidis and S. J. Youd, "High temperature acidic stress corrosion of glass fibre composites", *Journal of Material Science*, 32, 309(1997)
- (5) Hiroyuki Kawada, Akiyoshi Okada, Hironori Ueno, Ikuhiko Hayashi, "Stress Corrosion Cracking of Notched GFRP Laminates (Microscopic Fracture Model and Crack Propagation Rate)", *Transactions of the Japan Society Mechanical Engineers*, A-61, 2566 (1995)
- (6) M. Y. He, M. R. Turner, A. G. Evans, "Analysis of the Double Cleavage Drilled Compression Specimen for Interface Fracture Energy Measurements over a range of Mode Mixities", *Acta Metallurgica et Materialia*, 43, 3453(1995)
- (7) C. Jannsen, "Specimen for Fracture Mechanics Studies on Glass", *Proceedings of the Xth International Congress on Glass*, Kyoto, Japan, July 8-13, 23(1974)
- (8) Y. Sun and R. N. Singh, "Determination of Fiber Bridging Stress Properties by Debond Length Measurement", *Acta Materialia*, 48, 3607(2000)
- (9) Hiroyuki Kawada and Daisuke Inoue, "Study on Stress Corrosion Cracking of GFRP using Single-fiber Model Specimens (Evaluation of Interfacial Degradation by energy-balance Model)", *JSMS COMPOSITES-32*, 75(2003)
- (10) M. D. Thouless and A. G. Evans, "Effects of Pull-out on the Mechanical Properties of Ceramic-Matrix Composites", *Acta Metallurgica*, 36(1988), pp.512-522
- (11) H. L. Oh and I. Finnie, "On the Location of Fracture in Brittle Solids-I", *International Journal of Fracture Mechanics*, 6, 287(1970),
- (12) B. Budiansky, J. W. Hutchinson and A. G. Evans, "Matrix Fracture in Fiber-Reinforced Ceramics", *Journal of the Mechanics Physics and Solids*, 34, 167(1986)
- (13) Z. Xia, W. A. Curtin, "Tough-to-brittle transitions in ceramic-matrix composites with increasing interfacial shear stress", *Acta Materialia*, 48, 4879(2000)